

Efficient catalytic oxidation of internal alkenes, aromatic hydrocarbons and alcohols by using orthometallated and non-orthometallated Pd^{II} complexes

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Abstract : Pd^{II} complexes of azobenzene and anthranilic acid were found most efficient towards the catalytic oxidation of internal alkenes, aromatic hydrocarbons and alcohol in DMF-C₂H₅OH (6 : 4) mixed solvent system both under normal and high pressure of molecular oxygen. No diminished catalytic activity was observed even after 6-8 repeated catalytic runs. Effect of extra ligand on the rate of oxidation, nature and percentage yield of products was investigated.

Keywords : Pd^{II} complexes, catalytic oxidation, internal alkene, aromatic hydrocarbons, alcohol.

Introduction

Catalytic oxidation of various organic compounds leads to important products and find application in all areas of chemical industries¹⁻¹⁵. Acetaldehyde, *p*-xylene, toluene, benzene are the parent compounds for the manufacture of million tonnes of valuable polymers and solvents and again these are mainly produced via the catalytic oxidation of the above substrates by molecular oxygen²⁻⁷. Transition metals having different oxidation states can readily interact with dioxygen, even to the extent of forming isolable oxygen adducts¹⁶⁻²⁸.

The metal centers (either in finely dispersed forms or in their salt or complex form) are commonly used for oxidation of different organic substrates²⁹⁻⁴⁵. Besides molecular oxygen, H₂O₂, iodosylbenzene, pyridine-*N*-oxide, *t*-BuOOH etc. have also been used as oxidants^{46,47}. Large numbers of Pd^{II} non-orthometallated and orthometallated complexes are reported to exhibit very good catalytic activity towards oxidation of wide variety of organic compounds⁴⁸⁻⁵¹. Catalytic potentiality of a good number of Pd^{II} complexes of single and mixed ligand complexes have been studied both under normal and high pressure of molecular oxygen. *t*-BuOOH and hydrogen peroxide were also used as oxidant or as co-oxidant with molecular oxygen. The present paper reports the success-

ful use of Pd^{II} complexes of azobenzene and anthranilic acid for the catalytic oxidation of internal alkenes, terminal alkenes and alcohols.

Results and discussion

Pd^{II} complexes such as [Pd₂(Az)₂(Cl)₂], [Pd₂(An)₂(Cl)₂] and [Pd₂(AzN)₂(Cl)₂] were used as catalysts for the catalytic oxidation of internal alkenes, terminal alkenes, aromatic hydrocarbons and alcohols in DMF-C₂H₅OH (6 : 4) mixed solvent system both under normal and high pressure conditions. The rate of oxidation at 1 atmospheric pressure and at 30 °C was quite slow whereas comparatively high catalytic activity was observed at higher temperature and at high pressure of molecular oxygen. The nature of products for a particular substrate using different Pd^{II} complexes as catalyst were found almost same but the yield of products obtained were dependent on the nature of catalyst. The initial rate of oxidation, initial turn over number with % yield of products for the oxidation of styrene and cyclohexene with different Pd^{II} complexes under identical experimental condition are presented in Table 1. On the basis of initial rate of oxidation and initial turn over number, different Pd^{II} complexes used as catalysts may be arranged in the following order in accordance to their catalytic activities.

In the present investigation catalytic oxidation of different substrate in details were carried out with the most active catalyst $[\text{Pd}_2(\text{Az})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$. Reaction condition along with the initial turn over number, nature and % yield of products for catalytic oxidation of different substrate at 1 atm. pressure and at 30 °C are given in Table 2. Substantial amount of catalytic activity was observed at high temperature and high pressure of molecular oxygen. Reaction condition, initial turn over number, nature and % yield of products for different substrates at high pressure condition are given in Table 3. In all cases at the end of reaction, the mol % of conversion was always found more than 94%. Considering better reproducibility of the result, in Table 2 the % yield of products at the end of 8 h are reported.

Among the different organic solvents, DMF- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (6 : 4) mixed solvent system was found best both in terms of higher rate of oxidation and as well as in terms of

stability and reproducibility of complexes which was established by their repeated use for the oxidation of a particular substrate. The catalytic activity of Pd^{II} complexes in pure DMF and DMSO medium was very fast with the slow decomposition of complexes within an hour or so. No significant catalytic activity was observed either in CH_2Cl_2 or in benzene. The nature of product obtained for a particular substrate, both under normal and high pressure of molecular oxygen were found almost same (Tables 2 and 3). Only difference was observed in the rate of oxidation.

Styrene was oxidized mainly to benzaldehyde, with benzoic acid and styrene oxide as minor products. The mol % of products formed with time is given in Fig. 1. Cyclohexene was oxidized to 2-cyclohexen-1-ol, 2-cyclohexen-1-one and cyclohexene oxide. 2-Cyclohexen-1-one was formed only after the accumulation of 60 mol % of 2-cyclohexen-1-ol in the product mixture. Mol % of

Table 1. Relative activities of the Pd^{II} complexes as oxidation catalysts in high pressure of molecular oxygen

Catalyst	[Subs.] (mol/L)	Pressure (10^3 KNm^{-2})	Initial rate of oxidation (10^{-5} mol/min)	Initial turn over no. (min^{-1})	Product with % yield
	Styrene ^a				
$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{Az})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$	0.87	4.14	9.95	26	Benzaldehyde 82 Styrene oxide 8 Benzoic acid 4
$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{An})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$	0.87	4.14	8.5	22	Benzaldehyde 82 Styrene oxide 8 Benzoic acid 4
$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{AzN})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$	0.87	4.14	6.5	18	Benzaldehyde 82 Styrene oxide 8 Benzoic acid 4
	Cyclohexene ^b				
$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{Az})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$	0.79	4.83	9.04	21	2-Cyclohexen-1-ol 72 2-Cyclohexen-1-one 10 Cyclohexene oxide 7
$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{An})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$	0.79	4.83	7.5	18	2-Cyclohexen-1-ol 72 2-Cyclohexen-1-one 10 Cyclohexene oxide 7
$[\text{Pd}_2(\text{AzN})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$	0.79	4.83	5.0	15	2-Cyclohexen-1-ol 72 2-Cyclohexen-1-one 10 Cyclohexene oxide 7

Medium = DMF- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (6 : 4), [Cat.] = $2.56 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol/L}$, Total volume = 15 ml, ^atemp. = 60 °C, ^btemp. = 50 °C.

Table 2. Catalytic oxidation of organic substrates in DMF-C₂H₅OH (6 : 4) mixed solvent system using [Pd₂(Az)₂(Cl)₂] as catalyst at 1 atm. pressure of molecular oxygen and at 30 °C

Substrate	[Cat.] (10 ⁻⁴ mol/L)	[Subs.] (mol/L)	Initial turn over no. (min ⁻¹)	Nature of products with % yield at end of 8 h
Styrene	4.62	0.87	6	Benzaldehyde 55 Styrene oxide 4 Benzoic acid 2
Cyclohexene	4.62	0.98	5	2-Cyclohexen-1-ol 51 2-Cyclohexen-1-one 3 Cyclohexene oxide 2
Toluene	5.65	0.94	1	Benzaldehyde 32 Benzoic acid 2
1-Propanol	4.62	1.33	1.7	1-Propanal 34
2-Propanol	4.62	1.30	0.9	Acetone 27
1-Butanol	4.62	1.09	1.4	1-Butanal 31
Cyclohexanol	5.14	0.96	1.5	Cyclohexanone 31
Benzyl alcohol	4.62	0.96	1	Benzaldehyde 28

Table 3. Catalytic oxidation of organic substrates in DMF : C₂H₅OH (6 : 4) mixed solvent system using [Pd₂(Az)₂(Cl)₂] as catalyst at high pressure of molecular oxygen

Substrate	[Cat.] (10 ⁻⁴ mol/L)	[Subs.] (mol/L)	Pressure (10 ³ × KNm ⁻²)	Temp. (°C)	Initial turn over no. (min ⁻¹)	Reaction time (min)	Nature of products with % yield
Styrene	2.56	0.87	4.14	60	26	145	Benzaldehyde 82 Styrene oxide 8 Benzoic acid 2
Cyclohexene	2.56	0.98	4.48	60	23	180	2-Cyclohexen-1-ol 72 2-Cyclohexen-1-one 10 Cyclohexene oxide 7
Toluene	3.59	0.94	4.83	80	12	215	Benzaldehyde 86 Benzoic acid 4
1-Propanol	4.62	1.33	5.52	40	15	200	1-Propanal 88
2-Propanol	4.62	1.30	5.52	45	12	210	Acetone 87
1-Butanol	4.62	1.09	5.52	45	13	210	1-Butanal 82
Cyclohexanol	5.65	0.96	5.52	50	15	205	Cyclohexanone 90
Benzyl alcohol	5.14	0.96	5.58	50	11	220	Benzaldehyde 92

product distribution with time for the catalytic oxidation of cyclohexene is given in Fig. 2. Toluene was oxidized mainly to benzaldehyde with benzoic acid as minor product. The formation of benzoic acid in reaction mixture was detected only after the accumulation of substantial amount of benzaldehyde in the reaction mixture. It seemed benzoic acid is the secondary product of toluene. Mol % of product distribution with is given in Fig. 3.

With [Pd₂(Az)₂(Cl)₂] as catalyst the substrate may be

arranged in the following order in accordance to their initial rate of oxidation.

styrene > cyclohexene > 1-propanol > toluene

Styrene was found to oxidize more quickly than alcohol. In order to investigate the possibility that a free radical mechanism was occurring this oxidation reaction were also carried out in presence of 4-methyl-2,6-di-*t*-butylphenol (3.1 × 10⁻² mol/L). No significant changes were observed in the profiles of mol % of conversion and

Fig. 1. Catalytic oxidation of styrene using $[\text{Pd}_2(\text{Az})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$ in DMF- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (6 : 4) mixed solvent at 60°C and $4.14 \times 10^3 \text{ KNm}^{-2}$ pressure of oxygen.

Fig. 2. Catalytic oxidation of cyclohexene using $[\text{Pd}_2(\text{Az})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$ in DMF- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (6 : 4) mixed solvent at 60°C and $4.48 \times 10^3 \text{ KNm}^{-2}$ pressure of oxygen.

Fig. 3. Catalytic oxidation of toluene using $[\text{Pd}_2(\text{Az})_2(\text{Cl})_2]$ in DMF- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (6 : 4) mixed solvent at 80°C and $4.83 \times 10^3 \text{ KNm}^{-2}$ pressure of oxygen.

the product formation.

Effect of solvent, temperature, acid and extra ligand :

The effect of solvent on the rate of oxidation and on the nature of product was also investigated. DMF, DMSO, CH_3CN , methanol, ethanol, benzene and dichloromethane were used for the purpose but the best catalytic activity

was found in DMF- $\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{OH}$ (6 : 4) mixed solvent system. The catalytic activities of Pd^{II} complexes were found to increase upto 60°C under normal pressure condition. Above 60°C the rate of oxidation was found to decrease with the noticeable decomposition of complexes. As a consequence of this at normal pressure, catalytic oxidation was carried out mainly at 30°C and it was considered as suitable operating temperature at normal pressure condition. The rate of oxidation was increased significantly in presence of acid upto concentration (0.01 mol/L). Methyl sulphonic acid was used to see the effect of acid on rate of oxidation. In presence of acid greater than 0.01 mol/L, the catalytic activity of Pd^{II} complexes was found to decrease. Initial addition of the extra ligand ($\sim 10^{-4}$ mol/L) such as triphenyl phosphine, pyridine etc., decreased the rate of oxidation without affecting the nature and yield of product both under normal and high pressure of molecular oxygen.

Recycle of the catalyst :

Attempts to isolate and analyze the active catalytic species at the end of the reaction by removing the solvent, the unreacted substrate and the products were unsuccessful. This is so mainly because of the presence of metal complexes in the reaction mixture in very low concentration (3.85×10^{-6} to 8.48×10^{-6} mol). Again the active catalytic species was found to undergo slow decomposition during the process of separation from its concentrated solution. However, the catalytic activity of the residual solution obtained after the removal of products and the unreacted substrate by fractional distillation under reduced pressure of nitrogen was found same to that of original one. Recycling activity of the catalyst was found almost unaltered even after 6–8 repeated catalytic run.

Experimental

Materials and equipments :

Aldrich, Fluka, E. Merck branded chemicals were used throughout the investigation. Analytical grade solvents were always used and the same were distilled under nitrogen/argon atmosphere prior to use. Ultra pure quality of N_2 , Ar and O_2 were always used. Solvents were preserved on molecular sieves (4 Å) under nitrogen/argon atmosphere. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen were esti-

mated by semi-micro analytical methods. Halogen was estimated according to literature method⁵². Electronic and Vibrational spectra were recorded on Pye-Unicam PU-8600 and Pye-Unicam SP3-300 respectively. The product mixture was analyzed by TLC using silica gel-coated plastic sheets (Merck silica gel F254) and by GLC (5700-Nucon gas chromatograph, using SE-30, Carbowax-20M

the reported method⁵⁴.

Di- μ -chloro-bis(2-phenyl-azo- β -naphthol-C₁N')-palladium(II).

[Pd₂(AzN)₂Cl₂] (AzNH = phenyl-azo- β -naphthol) prepared according to the reported method⁵⁵.

Methanolic solution (15 ml) of phenyl-azo- β -naphthol (0.19 g, 0.77 mmol) was slowly added to methanolic so-

Table 4. Analytical data of the complexes

Complexes	Colour	M.p. ^a (°C)	Mol. wt.	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)				
				M	Cl/P	N	C	H
[Pd ₂ (Az) ₂ Cl ₂] (1)	Orange	280 ^a	389.52 (648.15)	32.11 (32.43)	10.68 (10.80)	8.67 (8.59)	43.18 (43.93)	4.14 (4.29)
[Pd ₂ (An) ₂ Cl ₂] (2)	Greenish yellow	200	347.45 (555.97)	37.55 (38.27)	12.54 (12.75)	5.13 (5.04)	30.32 (30.24)	2.05 (2.17)
[Pd ₂ (AzN) ₂ Cl ₂] (3)	Brownish orange	280	421.36 (780.24)	26.47 (27.27)	8.87 (9.08)	6.98 (7.17)	49.12 (49.26)	3.02 (3.09)

AzH = Azobenzene, AnH = Anthranilic acid. ^aDecomposition temp., Fig. in parenthesis indicate the calculated value. ^bPercentage of metal was determined by difference.

Table 5. IR spectral data of the complexes (cm⁻¹)

Complexes	ν NH/NH ₂	ν OH phenol	ν C=O	ν_{as} OCO	ν N=N	ν_s OCO	Orthometallation	ν OH	ν Pd-Cl
AzH	-	-	-	-	1430	-	-	-	-
AzNH	-	3300 3500	-	-	1430	-	-	1350	-
AnH	3420- 3315	-	1700	-	-	1100- 1300	-	-	-
[Pd ₂ (Az) ₂ Cl ₂] (1)	-	-	-	-	1440	-	720	-	320 340
[Pd ₂ (An) ₂ Cl ₂] (2)	3160- 3100	-	-	1580	-	1400	-	-	310 360
[Pd ₂ (AzN) ₂ Cl ₂] (3)	-	3300 3500	-	-	1446	-	720	-	330 355

or OV-17 column). Commercially available anthranilic acid was used after recrystallising from benzene. Colour, yield, mol. wt., m.p., analytical, IR and UV/Vis of the complexes are given in Tables 4, 5 and 6.

Preparation of catalysts :

Di- μ -chloro-bis(2-phenylazophenyl-C¹N')palladium(II).

[Pd₂(Az)₂Cl₂] was prepared according to the reported method⁵³.

Bis(anthranilato)di- μ -chloropalladium(II) [Pd₂(An)₂Cl₂] (AnH=anthranilic acid) was prepared according to

Table 6. Electronic spectral data of the ligands and complexes

Compds.	dd/CT transition (cm ⁻¹)	$n-\pi^*$, $\pi-\pi^*$ (cm ⁻¹)
AzH	-	22472, 27777, 31746
AzNH	-	19724, 21053, 24096, 32258, 3773
AnH	-	28660
[Pd ₂ (Az) ₂ Cl ₂] (1)	20408	28571, 32258
[Pd ₂ (An) ₂ Cl ₂] (2)	23400	29762
[Pd ₂ (AzN) ₂ Cl ₂] (3)	18018, 19531	26666, 32051, 37736

lution (30 ml) of PdCl₂ (0.12 g, 0.67 mmol) at 30 °C with constant stirring for 25 min. The mixture was magnetically stirred for 3 more hours. The reddish brown coloured compound Pd(AzNH)₂Cl₂ was slowly separated out. The compound was filtered, washed several times with benzene and finally dried under vacuum. The vacuum dried Pd(AzNH)₂Cl₂ was then stirred in dry DMF for 5–6 h. Slow evaporation of DMF led to the appearance of deep brown subject compound. The compound was filtered and washed several times with benzene. The reaction scheme for this synthesis is given below :

Procedure for oxidation :

Normal pressure oxidations were carried out in 100 ml reaction flask fitted with septum-syringe arrangement and high-pressure oxidation was carried out in a non-magnetic stainless steel high pressure autoclave. Procedure for oxidation was mentioned in our previous paper⁵⁵.

Conclusion :

Pd^{II} complexes of azobenzene and anthranilic acid derivatives were used as active catalyst for oxidation of a number of organic compounds. Among all the four Pd^{II} complexes, [Pd₂(Az)₂(Cl)₂] was found most efficient.

DMF-C₂H₅OH (6 : 4) mixed solvent system was found best solvent for these catalytic systems.

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